

Influence of University Organizational Climate and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the Influence of University Organizational Climate and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State. A correlational survey design was adopted for this study. Three research questions were posed and three hypotheses postulated and tested at 0.05 significant level. A sample of 508 respondents drawn from a population of 508 academic administrators in government owned tertiary institutions. Census sampling technique was adopted for the study. Tertiary Institutions Organizational Climate Questionnaire (TIOCQ) and Performance of Academic Administrators Questionnaire (PAAQ) were adopted and used to collect data based on the objectives of the study. Using the mean and standard deviation, the data were analysed with the Pearsons Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and a reliability index of 0.80 and 0.86 were obtained. The values of the correlation coefficient obtained were transformed using test of significance of correlation coefficients upon which decisions either to accept or not to accept the null hypotheses. Based on this, it was found that student's discipline, infrastructural facilities, communication style, leadership style, motivation, funding and university policy had significant relationship in the performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions. In line with these findings, it was recommended that more funding should be provided which is key to any effective administrations and be used for the provision of essential amenities to facilitate the smooth administration of tertiary institution. Effective disciplinary policies and measures should be stipulated to streamline the attitudes of students while academic administrators should live up to their expectations as role models. Furthermore, academic administrators should be empowered through professional development, involve them in decision making and acknowledge their expertise in the discharge of their duties. Moreover, channels and modes of communication style should be clearly established between academic administrators, staff and students and information provided regularly to avoid delay in programme implementation. Finally, infrastructural facilities in tertiary institutions should be upgraded to the level with the model facilities in academic environment by replacing obsolete ones while a maintenance culture should be adopted to enhance their life span.

Keywords: Influence, University, Organizational Climate, Performance, Academic Administrators, Tertiary Institutions

INTRODUCTION

The university is an educational setting where academic, non-academic staff and students interact and work towards the achievement of educational goals and objectives. A good result in educational environment, according to Herbert (2016), are achieved when a cordial relationship exists among the elements in the university environment. Infact, according to him distinguished some university, from the other in terms of goal attainment. Influence of tertiary institutions organizational climate on the performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions cannot be over emphasized. There are several factors that can influence performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions. A number of these determinants can be gleaned from the works of Likert, Dunhull, and Gardner (2019), as cited by Peretomode (2021). These factors include the size of the tertiary institutions, the leadership style employed by the managers or educational administrators, the communication style used to convey messages, the goals or nature of the tertiary institutions, the complexity of entire system, decision making practices, concern for employees, technological adequacy, motivation, the economic conditions of the institutions, students enrolment system, university policy and value system of managers.

However, Peretomode (2021) posits that a number of climates exist within an organization depending on one's place in the hierarchy and the climate in the hierarchy and that the climate of an organization like the university is a matter of impression. Based on this fact, Hoy and Miskel (2021) pointed out that the climate is the end product of the university groups such as lecturers, academic and non-academic staff, students and administrators, formal and informal organizations. Leadership and personalities of participants as they work to balance the organizational and individual aspect of a social system. Their end product includes shares values, social beliefs and social standards.

Tagiuri and Litwin (2015) viewed organizational climate as the milieu, atmosphere, culture, feeling, tone or the internal quality of an organization which enhance the effective achievement of educational goals. These qualities, according to Halpin (2021) distinguish one university from another. This point was made clear when he wrote; 'in one university, the lecturers and academic administrators are useful and exude confidence in what they are doing'. This pleasure is transmitted to students. In a second university; the brooding discontent of lecturers is palpable". The administrators try to hide his incompetence and his/her lack of direction behind a cloak of authority and the psychological sickness of such a faculty spills over the students who in their own frustration, feedback to lecturers a mood despair. A third university is marked by neither joy nor despair, but by hollow ritual in a strong way which doesn't seem to be for real.

The tertiary institutions as an organization is made up of human beings who work together in order to achieve the objectives for which it has been set up. This implies that for any tertiary institution or university administrator (Vice Chancellor), Deans, Heads of Department (HOD), Director of Programs to function effectively, he has to understand the norms, values and aspirations of his subordinates as well as those of the university or institutions. This according to Toby (2014) is very crucial because where the norms, values and aspirations of the staff are at variance with those of the university there will be tension and frequent conflicts. In order words, the culture of the institutions must be congruent with members of staff in order that the goals for which the institutions is established are effectively accomplished. The culture of the tertiary institutions in this regard is inferred from what people say, do and think within the organizational setting, regarding and transmitting knowledge, beliefs and patterns of behavior over a period of time (Knoontz, 2017). Clearly, tertiary institution organizational climate is multi-dimensional and influences many individuals including students, parents, school personnel and the community. Additionally, school climate can significantly impact on educational performance. It can have a positive influence on the health of the learning environment or a significant barrier to learning.

However, tertiary institutions administrators are not standing outside the organization. They are part of the problem as well as part of the solution. The role of administrators and leaders is to: (a) manage the way they perceive situations (what they observe, how they interpret and assess situations around the situation within themselves – their hopes, fear, feelings, abilities and limitations; (b)

manage themselves and their responses (the way they think and interact with others – their decisions, plans, actions, and communications); (c) manage all the systems and processes (dealing with the broad rather than an arrow range of circumstance and events happening both inside and outside the organization or university environment. (d) manage the power they have and how they exercise this power in practice (Christensen et al., 2016).

Finally, research shows that tertiary institutions organizational climate can affect many areas and people within institutions. Consequently, research suggests that positive interpersonal relationships and optimal learning opportunities in all demographic environments can increase institutions achievement levels and reduce maladaptive behaviors (McEvoy & Welker, 2023). These suggestions can be accomplished providing a positive and supportive work for faculty and staff through professional development and learning communities (Christensen *et. al.*, 2016).

Concept of Administrative Effectiveness

In a rational system model since organizations are viewed as instruments for the attainment of goals, the criteria emphasized focus on the number and quality and the economies realized in transforming inputs into outputs. General criteria include measures of total output and the quality, productivity, and efficiency. More so, than for the other two models measures of effectiveness from a rational systems perspective take the specific goals of the organization as the basis for generating effectiveness criteria. However, it can be said that empirical school-effectiveness research has concentrated on production management, co-operation, aspects of culture and all sub-categories of the primary process. A more complete set of modes derived from organization theory, is considered useful to give as full a picture as possible of conditions that may be used as avenues for school improvement.

If effectiveness is recognized as being essential a causal concept, in which means-to-end relationship are similar to cause- effect relationships, then one may consider that there are three major components in the study of organizational effectiveness, the range of effect; the avenue of action used to attain particular effects (indicated as modes of schooling); functions and underlying mechanisms that explain why certain actions lead to effect-attainment. In view of these, Karen (2023) included most of the perspectives that have been raised by various author in his definition of organizational effectiveness:

Administrative effectiveness is the degree to which an organization, on the basis of competent management, while avoiding unnecessary exertion, in the more or complex environment in which it operates, manages to control internal organizational and environmental conditions, in order to provide, by means of its own characteristic transformation process, the outputs expected by external constituencies.

Relationship between Students Indiscipline Behaviour and the Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions

The school is one important agent that teaches the child discipline. In tertiary institution the child is not only taught how to read and write. He is also taught how to exercise self-control. According to Lavis, (2020) Tertiary institutions help students to develop self-discipline by teaching them such values and traditions as fair play, respect for others, freedom to search for truth, and the right of weaker subordinate individual to hear. Ukeje (2021) offering that, the goal of good university behaviours therefore is to build up a level of self-control so that the proper habits will be followed without the use of authority; self-control that will provide the appropriate atmosphere for work in the various school locations and situations. From the above submission, it is clear that the importance of discipline in tertiary institutions need not be over emphasized to avoid ruthless behaviour and other cases of indiscipline among students.

In the university environment, discipline enables the students to adjust to others. It provides them with cues to acceptable behaviour patterns that are culturally and socially acceptable which are appropriate for success, mental and physical growth (Orhungur, 2023). Adesina (2021) defines

discipline as “readiness or ability to respect authority and observe conventional or established law of the society or of any organization. On the other hand, Okoni, (2021) views discipline as “the training of the mind and character to produce self-control and habit of obedience in the individual”. For Henry and Agari in Okwori (2019), discipline is a decent and acceptable conduct which contributes to harmony, joy, success and an exulted sense of responsibility, respect for authority, love for orderliness, eagerness to discharge duties with regularity and promptness, a desire to be agreeable and helpful to others by moistening a balance in the face of most trying circumstances. According to Okoni (2021) from the above, two types of discipline exist, self-discipline and imposed discipline. While the former implies self-control, that is the ability to distinguish right from wrong, the helpful from the hateful and the good from bad; the latter implies a form of control by an external force. Thus, there is more to discipline than the use of force. It has to do with the inculcation of control, restraint for self and others, sacrifices, perseverance, tolerance and recognition of human dignity.

Therefore a disciplined student is one who conducts himself and behaves in accordance with school norms, rules and regulations. He is one who knows what to do, when to do it, where to be and what to say. Thus the purpose of student discipline according to Orhingur (2023) is to enhance peace and order in the school for the effective implementation of policies and programmes such as promoting teaching and learning, on a nutshell, students are disciplined in university in order to produce a crop of individuals who will develop respect not only for school authority, rules and regulations, but also for themselves and the society at large.

Relationship between Infrastructural Facilities and the Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions

Infrastructural facilities used in educational system refer to building or structures, electricity, water, teaching aids and equipment which enhance the effective or smooth running of a university (Maxson, 2015). He pointed out that the importance of infrastructural facilities is one of the pivot for academic administrator’s performance at all levels of education. Lawal, (2019) posited that the importance of infrastructural facilities cannot be over emphasized such as classrooms, libraries, laboratories, workshops and studio or gallery. They are vital enablers of teaching and learning in the educational process. These facilities have to be of adequate quality and quantity to meet the standard of enhancing teaching and learning as well as proper understanding between the teacher and the learner. To buttress this fact, Okigbo, (2018) pointed out that infrastructural material in university help to create a conducive atmosphere for both the teachers and the learner. They also make the teachers more innovative and interested in performing their roles more effectively. Teaching aids in this regard when used accordingly motivates students learning and encourage teachers to employ their initiatives thus promoting effective implementation of educational policies and programmes. Infrastructural facilities like libraries, laboratories and classrooms in most tertiary institutions in Nigeria are nothing to write home about (Michael, 2014). The dearth of infrastructural facilities is a case point which has not received the needed attention by the government. According to Stolp and Staurt, (2021), “no meaningful result and oriented learning in the university will occur in a vacuum, hence infrastructural resources becomes a critical input for a healthy university climate.

Writing on the essentials of library materials in educational development, Victor, (2015) in an article “Education and Books scarcity” stated that the library is a reservoir of knowledge and the availability of library and its stock in such a way to promoting the frontiers of knowledge in any School system, that a society that lacks essential reading and instructional materials cannot attain perfect and efficient educational standards. Books indubitably are the principal means by which knowledge is passed from generation to generation. Indeed, books are mans’ only greatest weapon against illiteracy and ignorance, play a vital role in any educational system. Thus the availability and abundance of reading materials are the hallmarks of standard educational system in any society while its scarcity or inadequacies evince a faulty educational planning. According to Victor, such a society cannot only produce an ignorant people incapable of engendering meaningful economic and social regeneration.

Relationship between Communication Style and the Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions

Communication according to Peretomode, (2021) has several definitions and equally acceptable meaning. The term denotes both interaction and purposefulness. Basically, communication according to him is defined as the transfer of information, feelings or messages from a source to a receiver. Communication style is an inseparable aspect of human existence because people communicate from morning to night. To this end, man has been described by Okoni, (2021) as a communicating animal. It is the most important aspect of human survival skill because we need it to maintain contact with the world. People only get to know the outside world when they receive stimuli from the outside world and interpret these stimuli through the central nervous system. Communication as a concept is indeed an enigma. Thus, communication in a School is successful to the extent to which a sender of a message and a receiver have a very similar comprehension of the content of the message.

In the School system, there are usually interactions between the various groups that exist within it. This is important if the goals of the organization are to be realized. In the school, nothing will happen except people are able to communicate with one another. Through the transmission of information, ideas, attitudes, people and their activities can be coordinated in the pursuit of organization such as university and individual goals. For instance, the students who are the inputs in the school need to understand what the organization expect of them and how it plans to achieve its objectives are very important. Whether the school considers the students' contributions important and satisfactory depends on the efficiency of the communication style of the administrator. For example, the announcement of resumption date and academic calendar to students through various channels in a way that the students will understand is very important. This enables the students to adjust themselves to the guidelines in the university and work in conformity with the calendar. This promotes organizational efficiency and effectiveness without undue influence from any source use what is intended to be done has been made known to the students and staff on time. Besides, accompanied changes in the university calendar should equally be made known to staff and students. This will prevent any form of unrest in the system. Okoroma, (2020) stated that the primary function of communication in the university is to influence behaviour in a way that is conducive in the attainment of the objectives of the institution. Therefore, communication in the university is a form of human communication because human beings are involved.

When a decision is made in a university, it must be communicated to all its sub-systems affected by it. Communication pervades organizations because most organizational processes require communication to solve problem and accomplish its goals. Therefore, in order to persuade, instruct, direct, request, present and stimulate or develop an understanding in the school system, the administrator must communicate effectively (Gibson, 2023). According to Richard, (2017) Communication that is misplaced, inaccurate or incomplete will not lead to the desired outcome, however well intentioned. It will invariably lead to mistake and poor performance as well as frustration and a loss of confidence the part of the staff involved. Clearly, if people do not receive the information they need in order to do their job, they will be unable to give the required performance standards. It is important that the information needs of the various groups are recognized and met to a tangible effect on the achievement of organizational objectives. The administrator in this regard is to discuss the information requirement with his teachers to know what is needed and when it is needed rather than assuming that they know what to do without effecting any change over time.

Peretomode, (2021) noted that of all management activities, none takes much time as that of communication. If communication is hampered, the entire organization suffers, when it accurate, thorough and timely, the organization can move effectively towards goal achievement. He posited that there are atleast four major purposes served by communication in a university system namely;

Statement of the Problem

Most tertiary institutions according to Lennon (2016) have expressed dismay over the poor state of administration. Basically, the administrators are faced with multi-dimensional problems such as indiscipline among students, inadequacy of infrastructures, poor funding, lack of teachers' commitment, poor communication relationship, leadership style employed by the academic administrators, method of students enrolment, staff motivation and university policy system are the major problems of the study. If some authors claim that these problems culminate in the administrative malady of tertiary institutions, then there is need to empirically investigate this issue so as to obtain empirical data for making an objective judgment about the extent of their influence on the performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions. Indeed, such an investigation is dearly needed given the fact that the identification of these influential elements of tertiary institutions organizational climate is very rare.

Based on this, the following solution where propose: that funds should be made available and reach to the appropriate authorities as at when due, educational policies should be effectively implemented to show action than words in terms of service delivery such as provisions of infrastructural facilities both teaching aids and other learning materials that can stand the test of time and complete in the 21st century educational world, academic administrators should ruin the affairs of the university system with high level of professionalism that will introduce a leadership style that will encourage an open door policy where by staff and students will participate fully in academic and non-academic matters for the growth and development of the tertiary institutions system etc.

There is a research-based-knowledge gap and that is poor performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions, which this study stands to close with effective and efficient administrative system that will be achieved through positive and effective implementation of policies in tertiary institutions which need to be filled empirically through this study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of tertiary institutions organizational climate on the performance of academic administrators in Imo State. The specific purpose of the study were to:

1. identify the relationship between students' discipline and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.
2. ascertain the relationship between infrastructural facilities and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institution in Imo State.
3. examine the relationship between communication style and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institution in Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were proposed to guide the study.

1. What is the relationship between Students' Discipline and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institution in Imo State?
2. What is the relationship between Infrastructural, Facilities and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institution in Imo State?
3. What is the relationship between Communication Style and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between students' discipline and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.
2. There is no significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

- There is no significant relationship between communication style and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research design adopted for this study was a correlational research design. It involves the identification of elements of tertiary institutions organizational climate which influence the performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State. The essence of the design is to gather the appropriate data that could help to make plausible inference and generalization of the results. The target population of the study was drawn from seven (7) tertiary institutions own by government with a total number of five hundred and eight (508) academic administrators, comprising all heads of academic departments, directors of institutions and deans of faculties between 2023 and 2024 academic session. A sample of 508 academic administrators was drawn from seven tertiary institutions owned by government representing 100% of the total population. Census sampling techniques was used. Considering the manageable size of the population all the respondents was used as the sample size for the study. The instrument for the research was structure in two ways which was used for the study to determine the relationship between “Tertiary Institutions Organizational Climate Questionnaire and Performance of Academic Administrators Scale. The instruments are titled (TIOCQ) and (PAAS). UOCQ has two sections A and B, section A was used to gather data on the bio-data of respondents while, section B was used to solicit response on the questionnaire items. It has 44 questionnaire items. While PAAS has 20 questionnaire items and was used to gather information on Performance of Academic Administrators. Responses on the Questionnaire, were anchored on a four point rating scale. Both research questions and hypotheses were tested and answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation but further subjected to t-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance with a critical value of +1.96, when the calculated value was less than the critical value of +1.96, the null hypotheses was accepted and rejected` when the calculated t-value was greater than t-critical value of +1.96

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between students’ discipline and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State?

The data analysis in Table 1 showed that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient value (r) was 0.84. This showed that there is a high positive relationship between students’ discipline and performance of academic administrators. This means that an increase in students’ discipline leads to performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Research Question 2: What is the Relationship Between Infrastructure Facilities and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State?

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis on the relationship between Infrastructure Facilities and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institution in Imo State.

Variable	N	Σx	Σy	Σx^2	Σy^2	r-cal	Remark
Infrastructure Facilities (x)	508						Agreed
Performance of Academic Administrators (y)	508	15324	16437	518492	594469	0.89	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis in Table 2 indicated that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient value (r) was 0.89. This showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between infrastructure facilities and performance of academic administrators. This implies that an increase in

infrastructure facilities leads to performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Research Question 3: What is the Relationship Between Communication Style and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State?

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis on the relationship Communication Style and Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State

Variable	N	Σx	Σy	Σx^2	Σy^2	r-cal	Remark
Communication Style (x)	508						Agreed
Performance of Academic Administrators (y)	508	16194	16437	578140	594469	0.88	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The data analysis in Table 3 showed that the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient value (r) was 0.88. This indicated that there is a high positive relationship between communication style and performance of academic administrators. This means that an increase in communication style leads to performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between students' discipline and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Table 4: T-test analysis of significant relationship between students' discipline and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State

Variable	N	df	r	t-cal	t-crit	Sig. level	Decision
Students' Discipline (x)	508						
Performance of Academic Administrators (y)	508	506	0.84	2.67	1.96	0.05	Not Accepted

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis on Table 4 revealed that the t-cal of 2.67 is higher than the t-crit of 1.96. The calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significant since it is higher than the given critical value of t-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 1 is not accepted and the conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between students' discipline and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Table 5: T-test analysis of significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State

Variable	N	df	R	t-cal	t-crit	Sig. level	Decision
Infrastructural Facilities (x)	508	506	0.89	2.19	1.96	0.05	Not Accepted

Performance of 508
Academic
Administrators (y)

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis on Table 5 indicated that the t-cal of 2.19 is higher than the t-crit of 1.96. The calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is higher than the given critical value of t-ratio. So, the hypothesis 2 was not accepted and the conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between communication style and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Table 6: T-test analysis of significant relationship between communication style and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State

Variable	N	df	R	t-cal	t-crit	Sig. level	Decision
Communication Style (x)	508						
Performance of Academic Administrators (y)	508	506	0.88	2.22	1.96	0.05	Not Accepted

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis on Table 6 showed that the t-cal of 2.22 is higher than the t-crit of 1.96. The calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is higher than the given critical value of t-ratio. So, the hypothesis 3 was not accepted and the conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between communication style and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State.

Discussion of Findings

Students' Discipline Relationship with Performance of Academic Administrators

The findings in research question one revealed that Students' discipline has significant relationship on performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State. The corresponding hypotheses one was rejected and concluded that there is a significant relationship between students' discipline and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State. This finding is in collaboration with Molotsi (2020), who observed that indiscipline behavior of students which influences upon the performance of academic administrators in tertiary institution is caused by lack of essential facilities which they struggle to use in the system. Other factors are: peer pressure from fellow students, moral laxity of parents, undue familiarity with students by staff and lack of security, lack of devotion to duty by staff or academic administrators as well as ill-motivated, unqualified and inexperienced staff and lack of guidance and counselors in tertiary institutions. These views buttress the assertion of Adesina (2021) who traces indiscipline behavior in students to university management and administration. The university management administration factors include; lack of facilities and equipment for effective teaching/learning and other curricular activities, obsolete curriculum (i.e.) not in consonance with societal realities. Poor admission Policy resulting in the recruitment of unsuitable individuals and over population; ill-motivated and unqualified staff; poor public relations in terms of communication, integrity, firmness and fairness on the part of academic administrators insubordination of leaders; lack of sincerity and devotion to duty, moral laxity, incompetence, lack of consensus on disciplinary measures, undue familiarity with students on the part of staff or academic administrators. In the same vain, the researcher also viewed that our universities or tertiary institutions should establish a well-structured and professional unit for

guidance and counseling that will be rendering good counseling sections to manage and control students indiscipline and discipline behavior that may affect their future career.

Infrastructure Facilities Relationship with Performance of Academic Administrators

The study in research question two indicated that infrastructure facilities have positive relationship on Performance of Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institution in Imo State. The corresponding hypotheses two was rejected and the conclusion was that there is a significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State. This study is in the same view with Howell (2022), who asserts that lower academic administrators moral and results to poor performance and comfort among students, academic administrators and university staff in general. It further showed that tertiary institutions buildings in the State are in a deplorable condition to enhance effective teaching and learning. That libraries, laboratories, electricity and water supply are not available for the comfort of staff and students. Finally, it was found that a significant difference exist between infrastructural facilities and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions. This is in line with the view of (Stolp & Staurt, 2021) that no meaningful result and oriented learning in the school will occur in a vacuum, hence infrastructural resources become a critical input for a healthy tertiary institutions organizational climate.

Communication Style Relationship with Performance of Academic Administrators

The findings in research question three showed that Communication style has significant relationship on Performance Style and Academic Administrators in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State. The corresponding hypotheses three was rejected and conclusion was that there is a significant relationship between communication style and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institutions in Imo State. This finding is in collaboration with Williams (2015), who observed that effective communication style in the university system serves as a control mechanism of the various groups as it enables staff to adjust themselves to the guidelines and policies in the tertiary institutions. It also influences behaviour and prevents indiscipline and student unrest in the tertiary institutions. Besides it showed that effective communication in the school brings about higher performance and cordial relationship among staff, and students and other level of workers in the system. Finally, communication breeds in team spirit, flexibility and sense of involvement in the school. This is line with the views Richard (2017), that communication promotes organizational efficiency and effectiveness without undue influence from any source because in order to persuade, instruct, direct, request, present and stimulate or develop and understanding in the university system, ideas must be passed from one person to the other accordingly. It was found that a significant difference exists between communication style and performance of academic administrators in tertiary institution. That effective communication enhances the managerial skills of academic administrators in tertiary institutions.

CONCLUSION

The availability of adequate financial resources is necessary for the effective implementation of policies and programmes at all levels of education because issues like the supply of lecturers, payment of salaries, provision of facilities like books, laboratories, table, classrooms and other teaching aids depends on the availability of funds. Thus in recognition of the cardinal importance of funds to the actualization of tertiary institutions objectives, in the preparation of individuals for useful living within the society, there is need for the provision of adequate funds to enhance the achievement of a healthy tertiary institutions organizational climate. University policy is an important factor that a healthy university organizational climate requires to put the necessary administrative issues on grounds. The policy allows the system to be autonomous in her decision and also encourage administrative effectiveness within the university system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the findings and conclusions drawn from this study.

1. The university management should take students discipline as a case of urgency to establish a well functional guidance and counseling unit in the university community where proper counseling section will be organized for her students to checkmate their indiscipline behavior within the university system and also encourage sound administrative system to establish effective teaching and learning environment.
2. The university authority are also encouraged to provide good learning infrastructure facilities that will stand the strength of her numerous students to enable the system deliver proper academic activities for the future of her students and pave way for effective and efficient academic administration.
3. Communication style should be clearly established and information provided as at when due to avoid decay/delay in the implementation of university policies and programmes.

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